

Fit-for-region blueprint for carbon scheme development

Report
D1.4

Project CREDIBLE: “Building momentum and trust to achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU”.

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CREDIBLE
EU carbon farming

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Executive summary

Purpose

This deliverable outlines a “fit-for-region” blueprint for the development of carbon farming schemes across Europe, with a focus on ensuring that future carbon certification frameworks align with regional needs, farming systems, and socio-ecological conditions. It serves as a strategic input into project CREDIBLE, contributing to the knowledge base for the development of high-integrity, regionally adapted carbon removal certification schemes, in line with the EU’s Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Certification Regulation (EU/2024/3012).

Intended audience

The deliverable is intended for regional and national policymakers, regional authorities, carbon scheme developers, agricultural advisors, and researchers working on carbon farming, soil health, and ecosystem services. It is particularly relevant for stakeholders involved in designing or implementing carbon farming schemes tailored to specific land-use types (agriculture, forestry), regional climates, and socio-economic contexts, as well as those involved in piloting or testing monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) systems.

Description of the main activities

To develop the blueprint, authors conducted a multi-dimensional analysis of both public and private carbon farming initiatives across Europe. This included identifying key lessons learned from government-led schemes and regional authorities, as well as insights from private sector and hybrid models. The research integrated inputs from Focus Group 1.5 meetings, stakeholders consulting, Carbon Farming Summits (CFS) sessions and literature review.

Special attention was paid to regional variations in soil types, climate, farm structures, governance systems, and value chain dynamics. The study mapped region-specific enabling conditions, challenges, and success factors for carbon farming schemes, focusing on the flexibility of MRV systems, socio-economic benefits, and co-benefits communication. Examples from France, Italy, Belgium, Ireland, Finland, Sweden, Greece and Slovakia illustrate the diversity of approaches and offer replicable models for emerging initiatives.

Key results

- **Regional variation requires tailored schemes**

Carbon farming cannot be implemented through a “one-size-fits-all” approach. Regional soil types, land use practices, and socio-political conditions necessitate adaptable schemes that reflect local realities. Successful examples from Emilia-Romagna, Flanders, and LIFE Climate Positive show how regional strategies can link MRV systems to funding mechanisms and local value chains, boosting environmental and economic outcomes.

- **Multi-benefit framing increases farmer engagement**

Initiatives that frame carbon farming as a multi-benefit strategy addressing soil health, biodiversity and profitability tend to enjoy higher uptake among farmers. Communicating these co-benefits through trusted advisory channels (as in the Label Bas Carbone and Carbon Action platform) is essential for building long-term trust.

- **Participatory and flexible design is critical**

Participatory processes that include farmers, advisors, and regional stakeholders in co-designing schemes foster trust and increase legitimacy. Flexibility in MRV and safeguards against penalization in uncertain conditions (e.g., drought, natural variability) are key to ensuring uptake and sustained engagement.

Research and practice implications

The findings emphasize the importance of investing in regional knowledge systems and advisory networks that can bridge scientific standards with local practices. This includes capacity building for carbon literacy, MRV training, and the development of locally relevant tools and methodologies. The deliverable also supports the idea that pilot projects should be designed as learning ecosystems, where both practice and policy can evolve in tandem.

For practitioners, the blueprint offers actionable proposals into how to design schemes that are simple enough to scale, yet have enough potential to meet integrity requirements. Agroecological living labs, cooperative based models, and digital platforms are highlighted as mechanisms that can bring flexibility, traceability, and legitimacy to carbon farming schemes across regions.

Policy implications

In order to support the EU Mission Soil objectives such as enhancing soil carbon stocks, improving soil structure, and promoting sustainable land use policy must embrace region-specific schemes that integrate climate, environmental, and economic goals. National and EU-level actors should recognize the role of regional authorities and hybrid initiatives in driving bottom-up innovations and ensure that CRCF implementation leaves room for local flexibility and innovation, while maintaining environmental integrity.

Conclusion

Deliverable D1.4 provides a practical and evidence-based blueprint for developing regionally adapted carbon farming schemes in Europe. It highlights the need for participatory design, multi-benefit framing, and flexible MRV systems, all grounded in local context. These insights contribute to CREDIBLE's overarching mission of enabling high-quality, trustworthy, and scalable carbon farming certification frameworks across Europe, aligned with the CRCF and the broader transition to climate-smart land use systems.

List of acronyms and abbreviation

EU: European Union

EUSO: EU Soil Observatory

FG: Focus Group

FTOP: Funding & Tenders Portal

DoA: Description of the Action

GA: Grant Agreement

CF: Carbon Farming

CFS: Carbon Farming Summit

CRCF: Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming

WP: Work Package

PO: Project Officer

EC: European Commission

MRV: Monitoring, Reporting, Verification

1. Project summary

This deliverable is part of the EU-funded project under the topic HORIZON-MISS-2022-SOIL-01-06, titled: Building momentum and trust to achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU (project acronym: CREDIBLE, Grant Agreement #101112951).

The main goal of the CREDIBLE project is to build momentum and trust for the implementation of carbon farming in the EU. This will be primarily achieved by setting up and moderating a network of initiatives/projects/stakeholders for favouring transparency, environmental integrity, and methodology standardisation in soil carbon accounting. Such a network will be responsible for pushing forward multiple discussions (articulated around three main themes: which practices; what standards; how to monitor) and is expected to evolve from a mostly technical/scientific network at the onset of the project, into a process catalysing policy making and business innovation toward its end. The transparent, open access, multi actor dialogues required to build trust and co-create solutions will be orchestrated around three annual European Carbon Farming Summits, which will present opportunities for the network to interact with the broader stakeholder community and grow to the point it would attract further fundings for long term sustainability. Through the action, four specific objectives (SO) will be achieved:

SO1) to build and disseminate a practical toolbox for promoting carbon farming, capable of taking into account local land uses, best practices, and multi-actor interests;

SO2) to identify options for benchmarking and selecting standards, certification mechanisms, and policy instruments for carbon farming;

SO3) to favour the establishment of a network of soil carbon data collectors and repositories to improve measuring and monitoring carbon dynamics;

SO4) to build up processes and tools to drive conversations for the upscaling of carbon farming. CREDIBLE's ambition is to support the European Commission and the Expert Group on Carbon Removal in the identification and upscale of solutions for soil carbon farming. Tables 1 and 2 provide further information on the structure and composition of the project.

WP#	WP Name	Lead
WP1	Practical knowledge and fit-for-region blueprint for carbon scheme development	11-BSAG
WP2	Navigating and selecting carbon standards and policy instruments	12-EEB
WP3	Existing monitoring capabilities as enablers of soil data collection and sharing	8 - UFZ
WP4	Networking and communication actions to drive Carbon Farming in the EU	15-CKIC
WP5	Project management and coordination	1 – SAE

Table 1 - CREDIBLE's work package structure.

Table 2 - CREDIBLE's consortium composition.

Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
Soluciones Agricolas Ecoinnovadoras SL	SAE	ES
Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore	UCSC	IT
European Conservation Agriculture Federation	ECAF	BE
Association des Chambres d'Agriculture de l'Arc Atlantique	AC3A	FR
Greifswald University	UG	DE
Ecologic Institute	ECO	DE
European Association of Remote Sensing Companies	EARSC	BE
Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung GmbH	UFZ	DE

Centre de Recerca Ecològica I Aplicacions Forestals	CreAF	ES
Cooperativas Agro-alimentarias de España U de coop sociedad cooperativa	COOP	ES
Baltic sea action group	BSAG	FI
European Environmental Bureau	EEB	BE
European agroforestry federation	EURAF	FR
Bioeconomy Cluster	BEC	SK
Climate KIC Foundation	CKIC	NL
University of Helsinki	UH	FI
Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food	ILVO	BE
Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria	CREA	IT
Agricultural Applications Private Company (AgroApps)	APPS	GR
Institute for Climate Economics	I4CE	FR
Ellinikos Georgikos Organismos - DIMITRA	ELGO	GR

2. Objectives and perspective on carbon farming

The first two European Carbon Farming Summits, strongly upheld the idea that EU climate action should ensure and support holistic sustainability transition in the economic sectors most targeted by the policy framework for land-based carbon removals (carbon farming). The idea of going 'beyond carbon' and adopting territorial approaches was further highlighted in the second Carbon Farming Summit (CFS), as concluded in the Summit report:

“While carbon sequestration remains a key goal, the summit confirmed that an overly narrow focus on soil carbon risks sidelining broader benefits. Attendees called for a shift toward landscape-level approaches that integrate biodiversity, water management, rural livelihoods, and ecosystem resilience. Carbon farming must be designed as a tool for systemic transformation, not just climate accounting.”

The multidimensional systemic transition function of carbon removal certification was already highlighted in initial reactions to the Communication on Sustainable Carbon Cycles (COM/2021/800), e.g. by the European Committee of the Regions (CoR, 2023). Looking at values beyond carbon, such as biodiversity, it is also a driving force in private initiatives, and biodiversity is seen to play an increasing role in corporate sustainability strategies and also in market instruments (Berneheim, 2025).

In the scope of CREDIBLE, carbon farming is addressed in arable agriculture, agroforestry, peatlands and forestry¹. Considering also economic and social sustainability, carbon leakage and food security, this yields the need to define a model that incorporates carbon sequestration in a cropping cycle in a way which is feasible and acceptable for the farmer from a practical and business perspective. In case of carbon farming, measures on peatlands and in arable agriculture on organic soils, transition to another crop or another type of land use may arise, in which case sustainability considerations must be looked at the sectoral or national level.

Because agricultural production has developed in unique ways across different regions, and due to the increasing influence of regional and local climate, weather patterns, and biodiversity, sustainable agricultural and forestry transformations must take into account regional specificities and opportunities. This is the core objective of the CREDIBLE project – to facilitate development of region-fitted carbon farming models. While soil type and pedo-climatic conditions yield effects of carbon farming practices at a wide scale, which should be reflected in baselines, objectives and definition of practices, this report takes a more systemic approach and aims to uncover and consolidate key elements for region-fitted carbon farming scheme development. This approach draws insights and examples from operative projects and initiatives, regional authorities and other stakeholders involved through the task, focus group and broader stakeholder discussions (summit, interim public consultation). The farmers’ perspective is incorporated as suggested by initial priority considerations of the focus group (discussion paper for the 1st CFS).

¹ Animal husbandry as a sector is left out of scope as the CREDIBLE project addresses soil carbon sequestration.

3. Methodological approach

The aim of this report is to uncover and highlight considerations from the regional perspective relevant for the design and development of carbon farming schemes and the CRCF regulation, methodologies and application. The contributions of this report deserve to be considered when one is concerned about adapting EU climate action to the different regional contexts, and aligning climate action and incentives with the objectives, needs and drivers at regional and national level, including regional agrifood and bioeconomy systems. We apply a broad definition of a ‘region’ or ‘regional’, encompassing to mean territorial areas within an administrative, pedo-climatic, agricultural system or a specific program/project based delineation, not excluding a whole country as a unit. Sources of information for the report consist mainly of the Focus Group (FG) 1.5 discussions and discussion papers as well as the cases and projects that the FG members represent or referred to. The members of FG 1.5, titled “Developing fit-for-region carbon farming approaches”, represent various European regions and initiatives, contributing expert knowledge and best practice examples on key aspects of implementing diverse carbon farming schemes and frameworks to advance sustainable carbon farming in agriculture and forestry. We also apply a semi-open framework of analysis and a subjective assessment of features, attributes and qualities to include based on the authors’ judgement of how to efficiently provide most value added and to remain true to the approach of relying on the FG as the main external informants. Desk research and external expert interviews have been used mainly for Chapter 5 ‘Components of a regional carbon farming scheme’. Also, when prompted by the FG, more insight or references on certain aspects, such as the regional authorities perspective or position, have been solicited in documents and personal interactions.

4. Experiences from regions

As outlined above, regionality of carbon farming schemes (CFS) deserves to be considered relative to a range of attributes that have a geographical or administrative dimension: soil type, pedo-climatic, biodiversity, economic systems, governance structures and policy. In this chapter we examine how these attributes shape the implementation of carbon farming initiatives in practice, using examples from across Europe to illustrate diverse approaches to designing regionally adapted, socially accepted, and scientifically credible models.

The transition toward climate resilient agriculture and forestry systems in Europe requires the development of regionally adapted CFS that are scientifically verified, but also socially acceptable and practically feasible. As various European regions explore pathways for implementing CF initiatives, a number of key questions emerge that highlight the need for flexible, participatory, and trust-based approaches.

One of the central challenges lies in building trust and encouraging engagement among farmers and foresters. Facilitating peer-to-peer learning and creating spaces for shared experiences are essential to demonstrate the tangible benefits of carbon farming and foster confidence in emerging schemes. In this context, participatory processes should offer room for flexibility, particularly in cases where farmers make mistakes or face unpredictable conditions beyond their control. Avoiding sudden changes and providing safeguards against disproportionate penalties will be critical to maintaining long term commitment.

Clear and simple guidance is another pillar of successful CF implementation. Farmers and foresters, especially those unfamiliar with research driven or experimental approaches, require transparent instructions and reliable frameworks that provide a sense of stability and direction. At the same time, these actors must be empowered to inform and educate researchers and policymakers, bringing practical insights into the design of workable and region-specific solutions.

Organizational structures such as cooperatives or forest owner associations can play a crucial role in supporting group based carbon schemes. These collective forms offer economies of scale, enable shared monitoring and reporting systems, and facilitate access to funding and technical support. Designing CFS that are simple enough to be replicated across regions yet flexible enough to accommodate local contexts can help scale bottom-up initiatives toward national and even European levels, while these bottom-up initiatives themselves can offer valuable guidance and examples on how to effectively combine context-specific adaptation, flexibility, and replicability.

Policymakers need to anticipate a range of social, economic, and environmental questions when planning carbon farming strategies. Ensuring alignment between farmers' needs, business interests, and regional sustainability goals will be key to mobilizing local actors. Identifying practices that are particularly well suited for group schemes such as agroforestry, cover cropping, or rotational grazing can further contribute to building collaborative models that are both effective and inclusive.

4.1 Regions/authorities & government lead projects and other initiatives

Regional authorities, national governments, and public initiatives could play a key role in advancing carbon farming by developing strategies, piloting actions, and creating enabling conditions. Their leadership potentially helps bridge EU level objectives with locally adapted solutions, ensuring that climate-smart practices are both practical and beneficial for farmers, landowners, and rural communities.

Carbon farming can be perceived as a climate-smart pathway for reducing emissions, enhancing biodiversity, and building resilient rural economies. The experiences of several European regions and national initiatives demonstrate how these schemes go beyond carbon removal. The lessons learned from regional/government lead projects show that carbon farming is most successful when framed as a resilience strategy, a tool not just for sequestering carbon but for building sustainable, locally grounded, and climate adapted food and land systems.

In **France**, the *Label Bas Carbone* illustrates how robust MRV frameworks, combined with biodiversity indicators and external verification, build trust in carbon certification systems. Farmers benefit from tailored advisory support that helps them understand their baseline, plan actions, and track impacts over five years. The requirement to exceed regulatory norms and the focus on biodiversity indicators provide additional environmental value. For farmers, this translates into enhanced soil health, and a new income stream through certified carbon credits, thus integrating environmental accountability with economic opportunity.

In **Ireland**, ongoing development of the *Carbon Farming Framework* highlights the importance of early stakeholder engagement. Based on public consultations, Irish authorities recognized that farmers must see multiple co-benefits as climate mitigation, biodiversity gains, and productivity improvements to commit. This reflects a critical lesson that farmers are more likely to engage when carbon farming is positioned as part of a broader rural development strategy, not an isolated carbon offset tool. Socio-economic viability and flexibility, especially in the face of climate variability, are vital elements to ensure wide adoption.

Finland's **Flexibility Mechanism for the Biofuel Blending Obligation** (government decree 364/2025) allows fuel distributors to meet emission reduction targets through alternative land-based measures such as afforestation, peatland restoration, biochar application, and improved livestock feeding practices. By integrating land use into

national emissions policy, Finland creates incentives that reward carbon sequestration beyond the energy sector, while ensuring robust MRV, additionality, and permanence. This approach demonstrates how government-led mechanisms can align carbon farming with broader mitigation strategies, development priorities, and sectoral flexibility. However, the regulation lacks measures for holistic sustainability and expertise beyond GHG accounting are not included in the mandatory requirements for the verification bodies. We interpret this being due to the regulatory scope, as this decree cannot impose additional requirements, going beyond this law, on the carbon removal measures.

The **Emilia-Romagna region in Italy** provides a compelling example of how carbon farming can activate local agro-food value chains. By promoting practices such as organic farming, reduced tillage, and pasture restoration, the region not only enhances carbon stocks but also strengthens market demand for low impact, locally branded food products. Regional schemes implicitly support processors and distributors by reducing supply chain distances and promoting sustainable sourcing. This results in reduced emissions, increased local value retention, and greater consumer awareness. In Emilia-Romagna, carbon farming measures help determine how public funds are allocated, ensuring that climate-related support is both transparent and strategically targeted.

In **Flanders**, the creation of the *Flemish Action Platform for Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming* is a response to farmers' confusion around voluntary carbon methodologies. Here, the key benefit lies in participatory governance based on farmers, advisors, and policymakers to co-develop methodologies that are transparent and adapted to regional realities. Rather than pressuring farmers into selling carbon credits externally, the Platform encourages climate-smart practices that help farmers meet their own climate targets while preserving their long term mitigation potential. The use of eco-schemes to incentivize compost use or strategic crop rotations shows how climate resilience and soil carbon enhancement can be embedded into CAP tools and linked to national objectives. Moreover, this bottom up approach builds trust and avoids displacement of environmental responsibilities.

The **LIFE ClimatePositive project in Italy** underscores the importance of tailoring carbon farming strategies to regional land use and forestry systems. By applying sustainable forest management across five pilot regions, and developing regional carbon tools through stakeholder working groups, the project ensures that interventions are appropriate for local ecosystems and socio-economic contexts. MRV protocols developed within the project do not only track carbon outcomes but also biodiversity improvements, highlighting the multibenefit nature of landscape level action. Forestry

associations are empowered to co-design new business models and strengthen their economic viability through ecosystem service payments, thus turning resilience into a revenue strategy.

Together, these examples illustrate that carbon farming, when properly integrated with **adaptive MRV, regional land use planning, and local economic networks**, delivers **multiple benefits**:

- **Environmental**
 - Improved soil health, biodiversity, and climate adaptation.
- **Economic**
 - New income streams through credits or eco-labelling; stronger regional food economies.
- **Social**
 - Greater trust in policies; empowerment through knowledge sharing and advisory systems.
- **Governance**
 - More inclusive schemes that reflect the needs of land managers and their communities.

Table 1: Comparison of regions

Case / Region	Connecting benefits farmer-region	Region-fit practises and MRV	Socio-economic aspects	Communicating multiple benefits
Emilia Romagna, IT	Supports carbon farming via CAP; links local producers to local markets	Uses MRV to allocate regional CAP funds; promotes low-input practices	Boosts short supply chains and promotes local eco-labels	Promotes soil health, climate, and market access together
Flemish Action Platform for Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming, BE	Involves farmers in scheme design; balances regional needs with climate goals	Eco-schemes with MRV; focus on locally adapted practices like compost use	Supports farmers' self-sufficiency goals	Raises awareness on trade-offs between farm-level and EU targets

LIFE Climate Positive, IT	Connects regional forest owners to national strategy through sites	Develops region specific MRV protocols for forestry and biodiversity	Strengthens forest owner groups and income diversification	Highlights biodiversity, carbon, and economic development/prosperity
Label Bas Carbone, FR	Advisory services help farmers engage in certified carbon projects	External audits based on baselines; includes biodiversity as MRV parameter	Provides financial incentives for farmers exceeding regulation	Combines climate, biodiversity, and productivity outcomes
Carbon Farming Framework, IR	Emphasis on co-benefits and alignment with rural development	Stakeholder input on MRV integration into national framework	Ensures financial viability through public consultation process	Public engagement highlighted as success
Flexibility Mechanism for the Biofuel Blending Obligation, FI	Investing in domestic carbon removals would yield greater benefits and reduce public costs for climate incentives.	Boosts demand for qualified monitoring, reporting and verification	Raises need to consider competition between different carbon farming schemes and different types of land-based removals (temporary, permanent)	Raises a question for raising sustainability ambition and ensuring co-benefits (e.g. biodiversity) across different individual regulations.

4.2 Private initiatives

Private initiatives are playing a vital role in advancing carbon farming through flexible, data-driven, and farmer-centric approaches. Unlike fully public initiatives, these initiatives often emerge in response to gaps in national systems or market readiness, while remaining closely aligned with EU frameworks such as the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming. Their key strength lies in bridging scientific research, practical farming

experience, and emerging market needs while respecting local conditions and farming realities.

The **Carbon Action Platform in Finland** exemplifies a system-wide approach to regenerative agriculture, grounded in science and collaboration. By involving 100 pilot farms across different soil types and farming systems, it generates high-resolution data on CO₂ fluxes and soil condition. This evidence feeds into an open-access platform, empowering farmers and advisors to make informed decisions. The platform embraces local diversity by tailoring practices to individual farm contexts, while its educational and policy advocacy components help scale successful models. This “from soil to system” approach ensures that climate mitigation is integrated with biodiversity enhancement, water retention, and profitability reinforcing trust and policy relevance. The comprehensive soil carbon sequestration system developed by FMI (Liski 2025, Vira et al 2025, Fer et al 2020) demonstrates how context specificity and global scalability can be combined in a scientifically robust fashion.

Carboneg, operating in the Czech and Slovak context, highlights both the ambition and challenges of measuring and verifying carbon accounting. While committed to scientific rigor, the initiative faces difficulties in reconciling variable field data with broader expectations of sequestration potential. Their strategy is shifting toward landscape-scale monitoring to enhance robustness and comparability. Carboneg advocates for harmonized international standards critical for attracting buyers from multinational companies, while also acknowledging the need to respect national legal frameworks and unique structural features of Central European agriculture, such as larger farm sizes. This dual focus on international credibility and local relevance is key to enabling future market integration.

Svensk Kolinlagring in Sweden operates as a mission-driven enterprise that blends carbon certification with ecosystem service delivery. Its two-tiered credit model offers flexibility for farmers at different stages of transition (one for tradable credits, one for transformation support). It emphasizes that carbon should not be seen in isolation; instead, it advocates for a broader shift toward bio-credits that encompass biodiversity, water management, and resilience. Svensk Kolinlagring promotes the idea of living labs and agroecological experimentation, co-creation and swarm intelligence to adapt solutions to local conditions. It also proposes aligning rewards not only with transition at farm level, but with achieving and maintaining a high-performing regenerative state. This is a concept that challenges conventional incentive logic and prioritizes long-term resilience over short-term gains.

CARBONICA is a cross-border initiative operating in Cyprus, Greece, and North Macedonia that aims to strengthen innovation ecosystems for carbon farming through the establishment of a regional Excellence Hub. The project brings together over 45 stakeholders through Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs) spanning policy, research, farming, and industry. It focuses on capacity building, entrepreneurship, and cross-border cooperation, as well as developing a toolbox of carbon farming solutions, certification and accreditation protocols, and strategic action plans. Aim is to promote context-specific practices such as no-till, cover cropping, and organic farming tailored to local ecosystems and crops, and supports knowledge transfer through the Carbonica Academy, which is an online platform for business development and acceleration of carbon farming start-ups. The initiative stands out for its systemic approach that bridges science, policy, and practice in emerging carbon farming economies, laying the groundwork for inclusive innovation and the uptake of carbon farming in widening countries.

The **AgriCarbon-SK** project represents a pioneering Slovak initiative aimed at filling the national gap in carbon farming governance. Anchored in the Nitra Region, the project focuses on developing a robust, transparent MRV system aligned with CRCF, supported by digital tools and farmer training. It seeks to overcome skepticism toward commercial platforms by co-developing solutions with farmers and research institutions, thus fostering trust and ownership. In doing so, it creates a pathway for Slovak farmers to access carbon markets or integrate climate actions into agro-environmental schemes. AgriCarbon-SK is a clear example of how hybrid models can translate EU goals into concrete, locally grounded solutions that empower farmers and enhance the resilience of food systems.

These private and hybrid initiatives share common outcomes:

- **Localized implementation**
 - All initiatives respect the specific conditions of local soils, climates, and farm structures, ensuring the relevance of practices and metrics.
- **Communication of multiple benefits**
 - Beyond carbon, initiatives emphasize biodiversity, water, profitability, and resilience, broadening stakeholder support and system value.
- **Evidence-based frameworks**
 - Monitoring, field trials, and data platforms underpin the credibility of these schemes, enabling learning and future scaling.
- **Integration potential**

- Through policy dialogue and alignment with EU frameworks, these initiatives offer testbeds for future public-private models and market mechanisms.

Table 2: Comparison of initiatives

Initiative	“Think global, act local”	Communication of multiple benefits	Evidence and technical knowledge
Carbon Action, FI	Adapts practices to diverse Finnish farms; informs EU-level policy through local evidence; co-creates practises and MRV in a way which maintains the field-to-EU-scale continuum	Communicates carbon and biodiversity as cornerstones for ecosystem health and factors of productivity and resilience	Robust long-term data collection from 100 pilot farms; open platform supports knowledge sharing
Carboneg, CZ, SK	Advocates for international standards while respecting Czech and Slovak legal and farming	Acknowledges variability in sequestration outcomes; emphasizes transparency and ongoing data validation	Uses measurement-based approach; scales up with landscape level data to increase reliability and comparability
Svensk Kolinlagring, SE	Focus on Swedish context but seeks alignment with EU CRCF; stresses regional ownership and national scaling	Emphasizes biodiversity, water retention, resilience; links ecosystem services with rewards	Builds knowledge through living labs and co-creation; supports agroecological transition

Carbonica, CY, GR, MK	Creates region-specific platforms to co-develop carbon farming solutions; builds strategic capacity in widening countries	Links CF to rural entrepreneurship, policy innovation, and capacity building; tailored practices for diverse settings	Develops toolbox of practices, certification protocols, R&I strategy; integrates science, policy and practice through the Excellence Hub
AgriCarbon-SK, SK	Develops a national certification compatible with EU CRCF; tailored to Slovak climate and farming context	Addresses mitigation, adaptation, economic benefits; supports farmer trust via transparent methodology	Combines MRV methodology, digital tools, and pilot farms to build national evidence base

5. Suggested components of regional scheme for CF

The elements described in this chapter aim to support existing and emerging certification schemes in differentiating themselves by offering fit-for-region solutions. This will enhance the participation of farmers in carbon farming programmes and ultimately ensure the effective operationalization of the CRCF at the regional level. In addition, regional carbon farming schemes foster a participatory approach and can therefore create a leverage effect among actors in a regional network. This is beneficial for scaling carbon farming projects through entire regions. Ideally, they also provide mechanisms for risk mitigation among participants of a carbon farming project, further incentivizing participation in a regional carbon farming initiative.

5.1 Eight recommended components of regional carbon farming schemes

1. Engaging individual farmers or farmer collectives in grouped projects

The primary advantage of grouped projects is the ability to reduce costs associated with carbon farming certification, by following the simple rule: the larger the project area, the lower the per-hectare cost of project certification. Moreover, by engaging in grouped projects, farmers can work together in a structured and supportive environment and can adopt carbon farming practices more effectively and efficiently, leading to better environmental and financial outcomes. Although the primary responsibility for designing a grouped project lies with the Project Developer, Regional Certification Schemes can support this process by collaborating closely with project developers in their region.

2. Public sector involvement in data provision

Establishing standardised baselines is a key area where public sector support can significantly lower barriers to entry for smallholders. Public research centres and universities bring value by leveraging localised, high-resolution carbon data and developing models tailored to the region's unique farming systems and pedoclimatic conditions. By ensuring that these data are used to better reflect the regional context, Regional Certification Schemes can help identify the key agricultural changes that can have the greatest climate impact, contributing to better assessments and the development of context-specific MRV systems. This provides a robust basis also for project specific baselines. Furthermore, public institutions can manage the network, infrastructure and funding to lead multi-actor actions both in the establishment of Regional Certification Schemes and in their subsequent management, acting as unifying bodies and facilitating cooperation between stakeholders.

3. Establishing and supporting model farms

Model farms are essential hubs for regional engagement, serving as benchmarks for validating carbon farming practices and testing monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) systems. These farms not only demonstrate the financial and environmental viability of practices, but also act as collaborative spaces where the Regional Carbon Scheme can work together to refine and scale carbon farming solutions. By identifying the

relevant model farms in their region, the Regional Certification Schemes will ensure means for a greater acceptance among farmers to adopt the best practices by allowing them to observe a real-case scenario. At a certain point in time, model farms, having pioneered carbon farming, may reach a plateau in terms of carbon removal units that they can earn. In this situation, a substitute financial compensation for these farms could be provided for their advisory role.

4. Identifying the most resilient agro-system changes

Identifying and promoting the most efficient combination of carbon farming practices, which are scientifically validated and tailored to the specific conditions of the target region is essential for maximising both cost-effectiveness and carbon sequestration potential. While standardising practices through a whitelist simplifies participation and ensures consistency, fostering innovation remains equally important. Therefore, while Regional Certification Schemes can ease farmers' entry by providing clear guidance on which practices are likely to deliver the best results, it is also their duty to encourage the testing of new approaches. This ensures that carbon farming strategies evolve in line with technological advances and changing agricultural needs.

5. Simplifying MRV methodologies

Regional Certification Schemes can increase the number of projects registered by accessing and providing public data for the delineation of baselines and project scenarios, as mentioned above, but not only. Additionally, regionally adapted strategies – such as: 1) protocols for Soil Sampling and territorial elements of the EU Soil Monitoring Law, 2) user-friendly interfaces for data collection, 3) calculators for estimating uncertainties, and associated net greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from the new practices – can make the process more cost-effective and inclusive for farmers, in particular smallholders. These tools help lower entry barriers and improve the overall viability of carbon farming projects. Regional Certification Schemes can then leverage their local expertise and resources to simplify methodologies and support smallholders. By offering tailored solutions and overcoming technical challenges, they ensure that farmers can focus on their farming activities, while making it easier to meet quality standards and obtain the data needed for MRV.

6. Value chain involvement: integrating inseting into scope 3 strategies

While participation in the carbon market is voluntary, Regional Certification Schemes play a crucial role in shaping the agroindustrial landscape by strengthening connections across the value chain. Regional Certification Schemes can assist agri-food businesses in preparing their greenhouse gas (GHG) inventories, helping them to set science-based targets and develop an emissions reduction plan that **include carbon farming directly within their supply chains, an approach known as inseting. By integrating carbon farming practices alongside their value chain, businesses can address Scope 3 emissions and build more sustainable relationships with their suppliers.** This alignment supports sustainability agreements between farmers and companies to integrate carbon farming practices and reduce carbon footprints along the whole value chain. Regional Certification Schemes can further strengthen these efforts by involving the regional government and jointly developing information campaigns, fiscal support schemes and technical assistance for businesses active in the target region. Greater collaboration between producers, processors, and distributors can facilitate the widespread integration of carbon farming practices, delivering both economic and environmental benefits along the entire value chain of agricultural and food products.

7. Monitoring and valuating sustainability co-benefits

This blueprint is based on the idea of a holistic approach in which carbon farming is integrated with agri-food and climate strategies at operator and government levels. Therefore, ensuring and monitoring sustainability co-benefits is a critical component in carbon farming schemes. Operators may use approved methodologies developed under other certification schemes, given they provide an approach for MRV of co-benefits. Several carbon certification programmes offer combined carbon biodiversity certification (e.g. Verra CCBS, ERS standard, Peatland Standard of Ireland, etc.) for improved land management projects. On a landscape (and potentially regional level), a set of indicators to measure societal, environmental and financial benefits of land restoration activities (such as carbon farming) has been provided by Commonland Foundation (a Dutch land restoration NGO). Currently, another initiative (<https://soilhealthbenchmarks.eu/>) is developing a harmonized soil health indicator monitoring framework for different regions and scales, which provides a solid foundation for the selecting and monitoring of indicators for specific pedoclimatic and agro-ecological conditions across Europe.

8. Regional financing facilities for carbon projects

In ex-post schemes, carbon farming projects create revenue after the first round of verification, albeit projects entail high initial capital expenses. Common experience among project developers of carbon farming projects shows that lowering the financial risk for project participants in the initial project phase is crucial for creating participation incentives. Regional certification schemes could help design and provide independent regional project finance facilities. These finance facilities could consolidate available investments for regional carbon farming projects and help lower the financial risk of carbon farming actors. For example, regional funds bundling private and public investments support project developers, lower opportunity costs for farmers arising from a shift to carbon farming practices, etc. This can help to spark more interest among all stakeholders. Funding structures for carbon farming may depend on the intended use of a carbon certificate or credit (i.e. for offsetting of private entities, contribution claims, or regional emission offsetting).

Roadmap to creating a regional CFS and key actors involved

Figure 1: Building blocks for a Regional Carbon Farming Scheme and Key Actors Involved

6. Future outlook relative with EU strategies and policies

6.1 Specific learnings regarding the EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework

Quantification of carbon removal units is a key aspect in the CRCF which determines the viability of the scheme for the operator and the value of the removal unit in the market. As the soil carbon content varies greatly between soil types (and across unharmonized classification and assessment methods), the potential and scenarios for carbon removals are highly context-specific. The featured case examples demonstrate how context specificity of carbon farming factors in, for instance, with respect to baseline rate of carbon sequestration, cropping alternatives as well as regarding information and data basis and MRV capacities.

Understanding carbon farming as an approach promoting a holistic transition towards climate-proof and circular agri-food systems, in which agroecological and regenerative practices are adopted in primary production, calls for adaptation to regional economies and agri-food and bioeconomy value systems. The FG shared the idea of integrating circular economy objectives in carbon farming, which could mean, for instance, seeking opportunities to replace mineral fertilizers with organic fertilizers and soil-C enhancing substances. For this objective, the CRCF should also aim at promoting local and regional circular systems by removing obstacles to more sustainable biomass circulation. This underscores carefully specified sustainability criteria and considerations for recycled fertilizers which recognize their additional and multi-benefits value at life-cycle level when integrated in CF, taking also into account territorial nutrient balances.

6.2 Observations with respect to related policies

EU Climate targets 2030, 2040 and 2050 and the Paris Agreement

The recent Commission proposal for the 2040 GHG reduction target (90%) as an interim target to net zero by 2050, if approved by the MS, maintains the Union's high climate ambition and suggests that climate action will intensify and continue to be supported through finances in research and innovation. According to the Commission, carbon removals play a significant role and option is opened also for international carbon credits (https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/qanda_25_1688). This shows a

clear direction also for everyone working in the space of climate action, such as in development of MRV, thus encouraging further cooperation.

EU Vision for Agriculture and Food

The Vision for Agriculture and Food (COM/2025/75) sets the European Union agri-food agenda and guideposts for long-term resilience in the sector. The vision recognizes the strategic role of agriculture and food and *inter alia* values inclusiveness and local and regional level aspects. Specifically, the vision sees carbon farming as an additional income opportunity for the farmers and the EU CRCF to increase harmonization between different measures to incentivize climate action and carbon farming. A recent study commissioned by the European Parliament assessed viability of the vision through four scenarios representing the spectrum of political mood and emphasis and concluded that the vision’s objectives regarding sustainable protein sources, reducing strategic dependencies and simplification and digitalisation are most likely to stand and be upheld regardless of the political climate (Vesnic-Alujevic, 2025). Increasing protein production implies crop diversification which thus, should be considered also in climate action and carbon farming strategies in order not to limit space for food production. Furthermore, the EU protein strategy is also connected to increased consumption of plant-based food, thus supporting improved climate performance of agriculture and food system as a whole. Considering the objective to reduce strategic dependencies, farming approaches which replace mineral fertilizers (for which the EU greatly depends on imports that the EU aims to reduce) with organic fertilizers and boosting of biological soil fertility can be aligned and incorporated in carbon farming. Thus, synergies with these overall goals make a strong case for aligning carbon farming with the goals of protein self-sufficiency and reduced strategic dependencies. This calls for policy coherence, as the study recommends, echoing the message from many stakeholders, from farmers to business.

EU Common Agriculture Policy

The discussion in this report about the significance of the territorial conditions for carbon farming warrant context- and site-specific knowledge in the implementation and adaptation of carbon farming at the farm level in agriculture and forestry. The EU CAP is the framework, together with conditionality with related EU legislation, which comprehensively governs context-adapted regulations, economic compensation, advisory services, data management and monitoring. As region-fitting carbon farming puts more emphasis on the ‘how’ than ‘what’, the CAP and it’s implementation structures provide a tested multi-level governance framework for the deployment of the CRCF. At farm level, implementing the CRCF within the CAP, would ensure the agronomic fit of

carbon farming practices and demonstrate the holistic transition objective and policy coherence.

EU Bioeconomy Strategy

Transition to sustainable circular bioeconomy is anchored in regional and local economies, land use and innovations. The role of local bioeconomy systems and pilots is well recognized and emphasized in the elements of the action plan for the strategy (https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/environment/bioeconomy/bioeconomy-strategy_en). It is, in particular, locally and regionally, that the Bioeconomy Strategy can promote cascading use of biomasses with the aim of maximising multiple benefits and value from recycled biomasses through their circulation, upgrading or spatial re-distribution (such as processing of carbon or nutrient containing side-streams or applying biogas digestate or other bio-based fertilizers). The quantification of carbon and sustainability safeguards should not prevent these opportunities for increasing the positive impacts of biomass circulation. As far as the CRCF has an impact on the management of biomass streams, their role in supporting local bioeconomy systems should be recognized in how the CRCF and the methodologies regard and regulate biomasses in the context of carbon farming.

Soil Monitoring Law

A provisional agreement by the co-legislators on the EU framework law for soil monitoring was reached in April 2025 (<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2025/04/10/soil-monitoring-law-council-reaches-deal-with-parliament/>). This law proposes to further harmonize soil monitoring so that soil health in the EU overall is restored, but MS and regional context and soil health issues are taken into account. The regional soil health baselines and trigger values for physical, chemical and biological parameters (whether arranged in soil districts or administered in another way) provide a spatial delineation and reference points for the setting of regional baselines for carbon sequestration for carbon removal certification in the CRCF.

EU Biodiversity Strategy and Nature Restoration Regulation

While the Nature Restoration Law provides for the benchmark indicators for the biodiversity co-benefit which is mandatory for certified carbon farming projects, there are opportunities for broader benefit in developing national implementation plans for the Nature Restoration Regulation (EU/2024/1991). These would consider the multiple functions of land use in agriculture and forestry and create opportunities for CRCF-

certified carbon farming projects that contribute to the biodiversity and nature restoration targets. This would introduce another mechanism to channel private environmental investment for joint biodiversity and climate actions. The CREDIBLE project deliverable 1.2 which integrates literary review, a meta-analysis and focus group discussions, outline considerations and proposals for carbon farming which aligns with food security and biodiversity objectives.

Horizon Europe and Soil Mission

At the level of regional authorities measures for sustainable land use and carbon sequestration in primary production and incentives in the value chains are becoming issues to consider and address in climate strategies and authorities are actively seeking cooperation and access to up-to-date scientific knowledge on practises and implementation mechanisms. Living Labs for collaboration, innovation, piloting and joint learning, central in the EU Mission for Healthy Soils, has been heralded by many stakeholders, also by regional authorities, as a beneficial and viable way of developing policy relevant solutions in collaboration between practitioners, research, the public sector, intermediaries and other stakeholders. Living Labs can innovate and identify ways to Introduce carbon farming within regional agri-food value chains and develop territorial approaches.

References and further reading

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Links to the featured case examples:

[Flexibility mechanism, Finland](#)

[Carbon Action](#)

[Svensk Kolinlagring](#)

[CARBONICA](#)

[LIFE ClimatePositive](#)

[Label Bas Carbone](#)

[Carbon Farming Framework, IR](#)

[Carboneg](#)

CREDIBLE
EU carbon farming